

A Performance Evaluation of Lightweight Deep Learning Approaches for Bird Recognition

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Abstract. Reliable identification of bird species is a critical task for many applications, such as conservation biology, biodiversity assessments, and monitoring bird populations. However, identifying birds in the wild by visual observation can be time-consuming and prone to error. There is a growing need for efficient and accurate bird recognition methods that can help researchers and conservationists to identify bird species quickly and reliably. In this paper, we provide a comparative analysis of performance of state-of-the-art deep convolution neural networks on a significantly sized bird dataset, with the aim of developing a more accurate and efficient bird recognition method able to work in edge computing devices. The results show that lightweight networks as EfficientNetB0 provide a great accuracy (more than 97%) and low time of response with a small demand for technological resources. Our findings could provide a reliable means of identifying bird species in the wild, which is essential for many conservation and management efforts.

Keywords: bird recognition, deep neural networks, edge computing

1 Introduction

Many biologists, such as ornithologists, may agree that birds are vital for our ecosystem. They provide several ecological functions: pesticide control, pollination, seed dispersal, fertilization of the soil, as well as plant reproduction [7]. According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), biodiversity, which is the presence of animals of different species in an ecosystem, is fundamental to sustaining life, food provisioning, water purification, flood and drought control, nutrient cycling, climate regulation [1]. All these services are vital to support human well-being and economic prosperity, which is the reason why many countries participate in promoting biodiversity conservation and sustainable use [2].

Due to climate change, many native species unable to offer ecosystem services at previous levels. It gives space to investigate future relationships among

biodiversity, ecological integrity, and ecosystem services [3]. Many countries join promotion of biodiversity conservation and sustainable use [2], while others study climate change impacts on biodiversity, ecosystems, and ecosystem services, and implications for natural resource management [4].

A bird image classification could be provided with automated systems. It opens a possibility for ornithologists to use high accuracy bird classification and predictions of spotted species using sounds [21], visuals [23] or both [26] for monitoring and preservation activities [8]. Bird recognition is a very important, yet difficult task considering birds have different appearances under different weather and environmental conditions [9], and all of these situations need to be reviewed and separately treated. Regardless all these difficulties the recognition task has been improved by members of the computer vision community [27].

There are at least two factors that confirm that the task of bird identification is not trivial. First, it's a similarity among different species, their forms varieties, but also image and sound background voices of birds and other animals. Secondly, it's insufficient experience of bird watchers which degrades the accuracy of species recognition [12]. These reasons led researchers to look around for more advanced systems to study bird species with as little human intervention as possible, in an automated way.

Because we can use fast and more effective training for machine learning, a search for the most efficient method of bird species recognition is taking place. Researchers are looking for an efficient model with reduced training time and can run on mobile or edge-computing devices. Not only birds image recognition is benefiting from fast models, but also behavior recognition [5]. While selecting the best solution for bird species classification, we have to decide how to choose a model in favor of better efficiency with several parameters (the smaller number is better for the performance), including hyperparameters, such as the number of convolutional layers, number of kernels and their sizes, activation function, pooling size (if any), number of dense layers, connectivity pattern, number of neurons, weight regularisation, dropout (if any), batch size, learning rule, and rate [15]. Moreover, these hyperparameters could be adjusted and optimized for a specific model, and that technique is called hyperparameter tuning [16].

In this work we contribute to the evaluation and comparison of deep neural network methods, thus optimized for bird recognition on mobile or edge-computing devices to test with images taken in the wild environments [5]. We computed and compared state-of-the-art methods evaluated with different metrics and used transfer learning and classifiers while achieving f1-score accuracy of 97.6369%.

Due to the environment where the proposal will be will be deployed, we should consider lightweight device located in the wild environment, so it can recognize birds' behavior, which is why we are conducting this study.

The remaining of the paper is structured as follows: section 2, Dataset Selection, will show how data is selected and why, where it came from, how it's processed; section 3, Model Selection, gives a quick look at the architecture of researched methods, their strengths, and weaknesses; section 4, Experiments

and Results, explains what experiments have been conducted and what results were achieved while putting emphasis on the target mobile and edge-computing systems so they are deployable in the wild environment.

2 Dataset Selection

In this section, we will show how we selected image data. This task was quite challenging as considering many bird datasets freely available on the internet, not all have quality image data that we can use for high-accuracy recognition of species. By quality, we mean low-resolution images, the dominance of a background component, and the position of a bird that could be distinguishable from other species. But the biggest challenge was to find a balanced dataset, with correctly selected training, testing, and validation sets.

There are a few popular publicly available datasets used for birds recognition: CUB-200-2011 (Caltech-UCSD Birds-200-2011) containing 11,788 images of 200 subcategories of birds species, 5,994 training images, and 5,794 test images [22], [23], [26]; SSW60 (Sapsucker Woods 60 Audiovisual Dataset) [17] containing 31,221 images across 60 classes, but also 5,400 videos and 3,861 audio sequences which make it one of the datasets used for multi-modal recognition [17]; Birds 500 Species dataset containing 500 subcategories of bird species, 80085 training images, 2,500 test images, and equally 2,500 validation images [5] [22].

In particular, we used images from the Birds 500 Species dataset [10]. This dataset is split into the training set, the test set, and the validation set, and contains images with a resolution of 224×224 with 3 dimensions (RGB), split into 500 sub-directories, one for each bird species. The sample of a few images can be found in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Random selection of bird images from the Birds 500 Species dataset.

3 Model Selection

In this section, we introduce the model structure to test it with images from the wild environment on mobile or edge-computing devices.

This work uses CNN models, such as ResNet50, VGG16, MobileNetV2, EfficientNetB0, Xception, InceptionV3, DenseNet121, and NASNetMobile. For each model, we used transfer learning and re-trained them to accept the new dataset called Birds 500 Species. We needed to find the most compact yet well-performing methods for edge-computing devices (for example, Raspberry PI or NVidia Jetson Nano).

- *ResNet50*. It is a version of the Residual Network in-depth architecture that combines 50 convolutional layers with 16 residual units. It has a jump structure allowing to skip one or more layers, solving the problem of vanishing gradient caused by stacking [19].
- *MobileNetV2*. It is a type of CNN designed for mobile devices. The focal point of this architecture is an inverted residual block structure (MBConv Block). The architecture incorporates an initial fully convolution layer with 32 filters, followed by 19 residual bottleneck layers [14].
- *NASNetMobile*. This NASNet is a CNN architecture created from enhanced cells using reinforcement learning. A mobile version is called NASNet-Mobile, made of 12 cells, 5.3M variables, 564M multiply-accumulates, and uses only about 23MB of memory [5].
- *EfficientNetV2B0*. This CNN architecture is a more efficient variant compared to the backbone model EfficientNet when utilizing a new inverted residual structure (MBConv) in the initial layer, utilizes less memory, but due to the possibility of the large size of a parameter also extensive use of memory [5].
- *DenseNet121*. It is a type of CNN that is more accurate and efficient to train. It connects each layer to every other layer in a feed-forward way, eliminating the vanishing-gradient problem, making feature propagation more effective, and reducing the number of parameters in the model [25].
- *InceptionV3*. It is a new architecture with improved performance on a classification benchmark. The fundamental idea is a mini-network replacing the old convolutions with the 8×8 , with two Inception modules and concatenated output filter size of 2048 for each tile, which makes the quality of the network relatively stable to variations [20].
- *Xception*. This architecture proposed as an extension of the Inception model by replacing their modules with depthwise separable convolutions. The Xception is 126 layers in depth while extracting important features and uses 36 convolutional layers. All fully connected layers are replaced with average pooling layers, resulting in a small number of parameters. The output layer using SoftMax and applied as the activation function [11].
- *VGG16*. The VGG16 model parameters are pre-trained by ImageNet, and selected as the initial values of model parameters for feature extraction, as per the specifics of data sets. It's constructed of 3 convolutional layers plus 3 fully connected layers [24].

4 Experiments and Results

In this section we present our experimental results with explanations for each outcome of the method we used. In order to extract the relevant features of birds, we used existing split of the bird data into 80,085 images for training, 2,500 images used for testing, and 2,500 images for validation. The models trained using the mini batch gradient descent algorithm, with the batch size set to 32, and learning rate at the 0.0001. Also, in order to avoid overfitting, five-fold cross-validation and early stopping were used for efficient hyperparameter optimization. The early stopping condition was based on the model performance if the model's validation loss function is not improving for 5 consecutive epochs. The evaluations performed using a 12th Gen Intel Core i5 12400F @2.5 GHz, 8GB RAM, NVidia GeForce RTX 3060 12GB graphics card, running on Microsoft Windows 11 Build 22000.

4.1 Results

We reviewed different studies to present models the most suitable for mobile or edge-computing devices. In this chapter, we show a process of analysis of 8 models for specific performance metrics before selecting the best candidate for deployment for bird species recognition. We conducted the training for the same number of epochs across all models we tested. We did that to speed up the training process. As a result, we produced four different graphs, each showing accuracy with the model size, accuracy to the number of parameters, CPU time per inference step, and GPU time per inference step. After applying transfer learning to the 8 models, we trained these models with our new bird dataset. As a result we are presenting the measurements in the Table (1) and in four Figures (2,3,4,5). We measured the performance of fitted models using a five-fold non-shuffled cross-variation-score as the accuracy f1-score. When our program starts, it reads all dataset images from a local disk into a matrix structure. Next, it downloads pre-trained models from a remote repository to a local disk. After that, for each of these models a trained on bird dataset was carried out using the Adam optimizer with learning rate 0.0001 and categorical cross entropy loss function, with a limit maximum 100 epochs for all methods for training. All methods finished their computation at different epochs: MobileNetV2 at the 46th epoch, NASNetMobile at the 91st, InceptionV3 same as Xception at the 63rd, EfficientNetB0 at the 54th, ResNet50 at the 38th, DenseNet121 at the 70th and VGG16 at 54th epoch.

The Table 1 shows 8 models, taken as the most performing from the types of available models, it shows sizes of these models (in megabytes), Top-1 and Top-5 accuracy in percentage), Parameters (in millions of items), CPU and GPU per inference step. Then, in the same table, the rest of the metrics is dedicated to post-transfer learning phase, which is: f-1 score accuracy, f-1 macro average, f-1 weighted average, and the last column shows placements, or ranking, of each of the models, for: sizes (1-the best, ..., 8-the worst), parameters (1-a little, ...,

Table 1: Model size, CPU time, GPU time and f1-score accuracy comparison with accuracy after transfer learning.

Model	Size (MB)	Top-1 Acc (%)	Top-5 Acc (%)	Parameters (Mill)	Time (ms) per step CPU	Time (ms) per step GPU	Acc (f1-score)	Macro avg (f1-score)	Weighted avg (f1-score)	Placement (size, param, CPU, GPU, acc)
MobileNetV2	14	71.3	90.1	3.5	25.9	3.8	94.4965	94.4340	94.4927	1/1/1/1/5
NASNetMobile	23	74.4	91.9	5.3	27.0	6.7	92.5860	92.5109	92.5818	2/2/2/6/8
InceptionV3	92	77.9	93.7	23.9	42.2	6.9	93.3258	93.2629	93.3314	6/6/3/7/7
EfficientNetB0	29	77.1	93.3	5.3	46.0	4.9	97.6369	97.6075	97.6364	3/3/4/4/1
ResNet50	98	74.9	92.1	25.6	58.2	4.6	96.5256	96.4640	96.5268	7/7/5/3/2
DenseNet121	33	75.0	92.3	8.1	77.1	5.4	96.3664	96.3042	96.3668	4/4/7/5/3
Xception	88	79.0	94.5	22.9	109.4	8.1	94.3872	94.3274	94.3817	5/5/8/8/6
VGG16	528	71.3	90.1	138.4	69.5	4.2	94.9741	94.9236	94.9718	8/8/6/2/4

8-a lot), CPU and GPU time per cycle (1-shortest, ..., 8-longest), accuracy (1-the best, ..., 8-the worst). To demonstrate how to read the results of the table properly, we take the first model MobileNetV2. According to the last column "Placement", it has the smallest model in size (1st place among all sizes), it's also smallest number of parameters (1st placement), it's also the most CPU- and GPU-efficient (1st place in both categories), and the last it took 3rd place in accuracy, with ResNet50 (1st place) and VGG16 (2nd place) outperformed this model.

4.2 Analysis of the results

We present a detailed analysis of the results comparing different parameters.

Results of the comparison Model Size and Accuracy. The first graph (Figure 2) represents a relationship between model sizes and accuracy, so we can see that ResNet50 has the best accuracy of 96.5256%, but at the same time it's not the smallest-sized method, as the MobileNetV2 leading the ranking of the most compact ones. On the other hand, the smallest and the worst performing model in our experiments as of the accuracy is the model is NASNetMobile. Another model worth mentioning is VGG16, having the 528MB in size, it is the largest from all methods we researched. The average performing models, which could be handy for a general-purpose bird recognition system, are Xception and InceptionV3, which are a compromise between a model size and accuracy.

Results of the comparison Parameters vs Accuracy. The second graph (Figure 3) shows the parameters of models with accuracy. We think the MobileNetV2 is the winner again, as the ResNet50 offers better accuracy but is not as size efficient as MobileNetV2. The average models Xception and InceptionV3, located

Fig. 2: Model Size vs Accuracy.

in the middle of the graph, could be used too, which gives average results for the number of parameters compared to accuracy among the models.

Results of the comparison CPU time vs Accuracy. The third graph, (Figure 4) where CPU-only systems tested for accuracy shows that the fastest and less accurate was NASNetMobile, but keeping in mind our goals, we need the most precise model available, with the best processing times, for CPU-only systems is available to us, it is MobileNetV2, with even shortest execution times. We recognize it as our best candidate for mobile or edge-computing devices without GPU.

Results of the comparison GPU time vs Accuracy. The fourth and last graph (Figure 5) shows comparison of models with GPU-enabled hardware and the accuracy of neural network computations. We can see that the computational times are much smaller, ranging from nearly 4 milliseconds for the MobileNetV2 model to more than 8 milliseconds for the Xception model. The MobileNetV2 is the best candidate for high-precision systems because of its speed, outperforming ResNet50, EfficientNetB0, InceptionV3 and even NASNetMobile, while offering 94.4965% f1-score accuracy.

Our measurements indicate that the smallest-sized models achieved the shortest computational times on CPU and GPU systems. Columns 8, 9, and 10 (see Table 1) show a percentage of accuracy sorted by the model size. Here, the "Acc (f1-score)" means the f-1 accuracy of a model after transfer learning, the "Macro

Fig. 3: Model Parameters number vs Accuracy.

Fig. 4: Model CPU time vs Accuracy.

Fig. 5: Model GPU time vs Accuracy.

avg (f1-score)” means the f-1 macro average of a model after transfer learning, and the ”Weighted avg (f1-score)” means f-1 weighted average of a model after transfer learning, the ”Placement” means a ranking of the accuracy of a trained network after transfer learning with our dataset.

5 Conclusion

After evaluating various deep learning models for bird recognition on mobile or edge-computing devices, we have concluded that MobileNetV2 is the most appropriate model, given its superior performance and efficiency. MobileNetV2 offers faster inference times and lower power consumption, also smaller in size, making it an ideal choice for resource-constrained environments. However, the actual choice of model will depend on factors such as memory availability, CPU type, and GPU type. Our future work will involve testing and validating our model using real-world bird images, with the goal of recognizing bird species and behaviors in the wild environment. We believe that our research has important practical implications for developing efficient and accurate bird identification tools, and we plan to extend our work to other domains beyond bird recognition.

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